

Cutting through the Noise: A Three-Way Comparison of Median, Adaptive Median, and Non-Local Means Filter for MRI Images

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Abstract

Medical Imaging is an essential practice in radiology to create high-standard images of the human brain. In medical imaging, denoising techniques are essential during image processing for a meaningful view of the anatomical structure of the images. In order to overcome the denoising issues, various filtering techniques and smoothening algorithms have come forth to get an accurate image for better diagnosis while preserving the original image quality. This work utilizes three computational methods for filtering noise that could distort the factual information in MRI images. The input used as the data throughout this study are MR images in grayscale contaminated with Salt and pepper noise, the most common noise in MRI images. To de-noise, a comparative analysis of three specific filters, namely the Non-Local Means filter, Median filter, and Adaptive Median filter, is conducted to do a study that gives the best results among them at different noise densities. Peak Signal-To-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) are utilized as the main components to examine the behavior of the suggested filters in this study. The results show that at every value of noise density, i.e., 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, the adaptive median filter gives the highest average PSNR of 42.04, 34.36, and 28.10 and average SSIM of 0.97, 0.95, and 0.91, respectively. Hence, it indicates that the adaptive median filter outperforms the other two filters regarding PSNR and SSIM.

Index Terms: Adaptive Median Filter, Medical Imaging Denoising, Non-Local Means Filter, Peak Signal-To-Noise Ratio, and Structural Similarity Index.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

During the process of acquiring, compressing, and transmitting medical images, they become spoiled due to the influence of ambient, transmission medium, and other variables. This causes distortion and loss of picture information [1]. Noise has a negative impact on potential post-image processing techniques like video processing, image analysis, and tracking. Sometimes, the mathematical analysis of image generation also uses noise to model the errors [2]. Therefore, denoising plays a crucial role in the processing of images. Denoising removes unwanted data or distortion without compromising the original image, and during the process of denoising, it is hard to erase some of the high-frequency components, such as edge and texture, which inadvertently leads to the images losing informative data. However, restoring the essential data from noisy photos to get high-standard images is a modern-day problem.

In 'Medical Image Processing', one of the important research topics is evidently 'De-noising'. Medical imaging is one of the systemic departments that helps in clinical diagnosis by producing both 2, and 3-dimensional body scans through different imaging techniques, so the medical images are bound to have noises due to disturbing artifacts.

Magnetic Resonance MR Images are also susceptible to noises while acquiring, processing, and storing data. Different studies and techniques of denoising and smoothing can be found in the literature, and analyses are still going on for advancement and betterment [3-6]. Small details, such as the edges of structures, must indeed be preserved during filtering, which might be important for diagnostic treatment [7]. In terms of noises that distort medical images, a few can be listed here, such as Quantization Noise, Gaussian Noise, Impulse Noise, Poisson Noise, and so on. For the effectiveness and standard mathematical formulation of the computational design, it is required to have some previous knowledge about the type of noise before constructing an algorithm for a denoising procedure [8]. Gaussian noise reduces the level of image interpretation by affecting almost every pixel of an image uniformly [9-11]. The Impulse Noise influences the limited pixels in a dark and white mode and leaves room for primary image interpretation. On the contrary, it is quite rare to come across some noises like Poisson Noise, Quantization Noise, and Speckle Noise, which may happen only due to the bit error rate, manufacture fault, or maybe insufficient photon count while imaging acquisition.

Salt And Pepper (SAP) noise is among the most common and unavoidable noises in MRI imaging. The noise corrupts the pixels to take the dynamic range of maximum or minimum gray value [12], and [13]. The white and black spots appear on the pixels in the corrupted image [14-16]. Due to the huge loss of information detail when the photos are badly distorted by SAP noise, retrieving detail is considerably trickier. Noisy pixels in the picture are replaced with either the greatest or lowest pixel intensity value, while unaffected pixels always stay intact, thereby causing the typical white and black dots (or "salt and pepper" noise) [17].

Below in eq. (1) is the mathematical expression of this:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \delta_{\min} & \text{with probability } p, \\ \delta_{\max} & \text{with probability } q, \\ u(x) & \text{with probability } 1 - p - q, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where:

The function 'f' is the observed noisy image and the function 'u' is the noise-free image, respectively.

The $[\delta_{\min}, \delta_{\max}]$ is, therefore, the range of $u(x)$;

Assuming that the image's intensity value falls between $[0,1]$ without losing generality, hence $\delta_{\min} = 0$ and $\delta_{\max} = 1$;

The level of the salt and pepper noise would be calculated by the probability $p+q$ [17].

Noise Removal is still a challenging task for researchers since it may lead to artifacts and blur the MR images. These artifacts can show in the image as exaggerated features lost fine details, or jarring appearances. Over the years, lots of research has been done to introduce effective noise removal techniques of MR images [17-22]. For the removal of salt and pepper noise, the median filter was first used in 1971 [23], but the drawback was that it used the techniques of over-smoothing the edges and texture, resulting in weak features. Currently, it is widely believed that the partial differential equation-based denoising method has a better effect on preserving the edge and texture area in denoising [24].

To reduce salt and pepper noise, a high signal-to-noise ratio while maintaining the edges and other fine features of the image is an appropriate method. To achieve this, an adaptive median filter was developed [25]. This technique ensures better image enhancement and that Secondary Audio Program (SAP) noise is detected even at high noise densities, but the window size should be large enough [26]. Windowing is a technique used to modify an image's grayscale.

Another method is to use 'Non-Local Means' filters and estimation to filter out the noise [20], [22], [27], which shows better accuracy, well-defined sharpness, and restore image better at high noise variance.

Evaluation metrics are an essential part of image processing and are used to assess the efficacy of various image processing methods. Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), two assessment measures, were utilized in this study to assess the effectiveness of the three filters.

A. PSNR

The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio, PSNR, is a frequently used criterion for evaluating the quality of an image or video signal that has been processed or rebuilt. Higher scores indicate a stronger resemblance between the two photos, which is how it assesses similarity [28].

Mathematically, PSNR is defined as in eq. (2):

$$\text{PSNR} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{MAX}_f}{\sqrt{\text{MSE}}} \right) \quad (2)$$

The mean squared error (MSE) compares the raw and treated images. It is determined as such in eq. 3:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_0^{m-1} \sum_0^{n-1} ||f(i, j) - g(i, j)||^2 \quad (3)$$

Where:

The matrix data of the original picture is represented by function 'f', and,

The matrix data of the reconstructed image is represented by function 'g',

The 'm', and 'n' are the number of rows and columns, respectively.

In contrast, 'i' and 'j', represent the indices of the corresponding row and column.

The 'MAX_f' is also known as the greatest pixel value achievable (in most cases, 255 for 8-bit images) in the original image [29].

A greater value of the PSNR, which is often reported in decibels (dB), corresponds to a higher-quality image. A PSNR of 30 dB or more is often regarded as "good" quality.

B. SSIM

Another popular tool for comparing the similarity of two photos is the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM). It is more reliable and robust than traditional pixel-based metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE) or Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR). The SSIM is an absolute reference metric, which means that when assessing or forecasting picture quality, the initial uncompressed or distortion-free image is used as the benchmark [30].

SSIM performs structural similarity measurements between two images by considering three important factors of human visual perception: luminance, Contrast, and Structure [31].

The SSIM index is given as in eq. (4):

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (4)$$

Where:

The x and y are the two medical pictures to be analyzed, Their averages and standard deviations would be μ_x and μ_y and σ_x and σ_y respectively and σ_{xy} being the cross-covariance of x and y.

The $c_1 = (k_1L)^2$, $c_2 = (k_2L)^2$ are two parameters used to strengthen the division with insignificant denominators

and avoid division by zero, the L is being the dynamic domain of the pixel units, $k_1 = 0.01$, While $k_2 = 0.03$ by default [32].

A higher score of SSIM indicates better image quality and higher similarity between the two images being compared. In this work, we compare the Median, Adaptive Median, and Non-Local Means filters to determine which denoising method produces the best results. The study is conducted in MATLAB R2019b and Python to ensure the robustness of the filters across different platforms, and crucial metrics are used to assess the effectiveness of the suggested filters, namely Peak Signal-To-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This paper utilizes different MRI images that include a T1-weighted image of a healthy brain [33], a T2-weighted image of a normal brain [34], and a T1-weighted contrast-enhanced MRI image of a brain [35], as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: (a) T1-Weighted Image of a Healthy Brain [33] (b) T2-Weighted Image of a Normal Brain [34] (3) T1-Weighted Contrast-Enhanced MRI Image of a Brain [35]

The three specific filters, namely the Non-Local Means, Median, and Adaptive Median filters, are applied to the above-mentioned images in this study. The Adaptive Median filter is designed in Python, whereas the other two filters, which are the Median and Non-Local Means filters, are designed in MATLAB. Afterward, the effectiveness of each filter is evaluated on several platforms by utilizing Python and MATLAB software applications.

Three alternative image filtering algorithms have been selected for analysis, namely the Non-Local Means, Median, and Adaptive Median filters. These algorithms were selected because of their popularity and propensity for removing salt and pepper noise, which is typically seen in medical images.

A. Filters

The filters that are used in this study are as follows:

1) Median Filter:

One of the most prominent non-linear filtering techniques for eliminating salt and pepper noise from images while preserving the edges is Median filtering. A window that slides across the pixels identifies the neighbors. The Median filter first determines a pixel's window neighbors before processing the pixel. The values of these neighbors are then sorted in numerical order from least to most significant. In this sorted list, the median value is understandably the central value. In the event of having a

set of even number of values, the median would be, therefore, an average of the two central values. [36]

Following that, the filter replaces the initial pixel value with the estimated median value. The window slides across the entire image as this procedure is performed for each pixel.

Figure 2: 3 Median Filters Applied to a Single Noisy Image [37]

2) Adaptive Median Filter:

To begin using the Adaptive Median filter, a window is created around each pixel in the image. The window is enlarged until a pixel that differs considerably from the others is discovered inside. It has been determined that this pixel is an outlier, also referred to as a noisy pixel. The window size is then reset to its initial size after calculating the window's pixel values' median.

3) Non-Local Means Filter:

In order to dampen noise from an image, this Non-Local Means filter finds clusters of similar pixels and averages their values.

The image must first be separated into overlapping pixel patches for the Non-Local Means filter to work properly [38]. The next step is to look for comparable patches by comparing each patch to every other in the image. The distance between the patches in the image and the similarity of their pixel values determine how similar the patches are. The picture is then given a smoothed form by averaging the pixel values of related areas.

Figure 3: A Picture with Gaussian Noise Distortion is Subjected to Non-Local Means [39]

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experimental results of the suggested Median, Adaptive Median, and Non-Local Means filter for denoising MRI images are compared in this section. The studies are carried out on three MRI pictures with three noise densities, and the quantitative evaluation is based on the respective PSNR and SSIM measures.

The denoising results for image 1 from using the Median filter to various noise densities (0.1, 0.3, and 0.6) are shown in figure IV.

Figure IV: Denoising Results for Image 1 on Various Noise Densities

The noised photos exhibit high degrees of noise, as shown in the above figure, making distinguishing between details and edges difficult.

Figure V: Denoising Results for Image 2 on Various Noise Densities

The de-noised images do, however, show a significant increase in terms of noise reduction and restoration of more information and edges after filtering.

Figure V displays the denoising results obtained from image 2 using the Adaptive Median filter on different noise densities. The denoising results from image 3 using a Non-Local Means filter on various noise densities are shown in figure VI.

Figure VI: Denoising Results for Image 3 on Various Noise Densities

The respective PSNR and SSIM values for these three specific filters, namely the Median, Adaptive Median, and Non-Local Means, for all noise densities over all three images, are presented in table I as the outcomes of the studies. The table offers a thorough breakdown of the denoising performance of the three filters, enabling a side-by-side evaluation of each filter's potency.

Table I simplifies the data analysis process for the reader and provides them with a clear understanding of how each filter performs at different noise densities on different images. This can be especially useful for researchers and practitioners who may want to use these filters in their work, as it can help inform their choice of filter based on their specific requirements and the noise levels they are dealing with.

Table I: PSNR and SSIM Values of Median, Adaptive Median, and Non-Local Means Filters across all Three Images

		PSNR			SSIM		
		0.1	0.3	0.6	0.1	0.3	0.6
Median Filter	Image 1	41.64	37.41	31.11	0.99	0.98	0.94
	Image 2	40.67	31.10	25.87	0.97	0.92	0.83
	Image 3	35.01	26.63	23.56	0.94	0.91	0.83
Adaptive Median Filter	Image 1	43.75	37.77	32.54	0.99	0.99	0.97
	Image 2	42.40	34.79	27.15	0.96	0.95	0.90
	Image 3	39.97	30.51	24.62	0.97	0.92	0.88
Non-Local Means Filter	Image 1	43.83	37.40	30.95	0.99	0.98	0.94
	Image 2	41.37	35.02	29.11	0.97	0.92	0.84
	Image 3	32.11	29.51	27.21	0.97	0.91	0.82

According to table I, the non-local means filter has the lowest PSNR, accounting for 39.10, whereas the adaptive median filter has the highest PSNR of 42.04 at 0.1 noise density. The non-local means filter yields the highest value of 0.98 for SSIM. The Adaptive Median filter beats the others with a PSNR of 34.36 at 0.3 noise density and a PSNR of 31.71 for the Median filter. The Adaptive Median filter likewise obtains the most excellent SSIM value of 0.95. The Median filter has the lowest PSNR of 26.85 at 0.6 noise density, and the Non-Local Means filter has the

maximum PSNR of 29.09. The Adaptive Median filter achieves the highest SSIM value of 0.92. These findings suggest that the Adaptive Median filter consistently outperforms the other two filters in terms of PSNR and SSIM, particularly at higher noise densities.

The finding of the studies offers insightful information about the efficacy of various filter algorithms for de-noising MRI pictures with salt and pepper noise. Our results show that, in terms of PSNR scores, the Adaptive Median filter outperforms the other two filters—the Median filter and the

Non-Local Means filter. This proves the Adaptive Median filter is superior at lowering noise and retaining fine features and edges in images. The Non-Local Means filter does, however, provide improved SSIM scores for low and medium noise densities, showing that it can maintain the structural similarity of the image.

The Adaptive Median filter's capacity to withstand various types of noise and adaptively alter its parameters to the local characteristics of the image could be one factor for its outstanding performance. The Median and Non-Local Means filters apply a fixed kernel to the entire image, which may lead to the loss of critical edges and details. However, further study is required to determine the precise causes of the Adaptive Median filter's higher performance.

Discussing the strengths and weaknesses of each filter algorithm used in this study is worthwhile. The simplicity and computational efficiency of the Median filter make it a popular method. It is simple to apply and only takes a little while to process. The Median filter can blur edges and features, while it is not very good at decreasing high-density noise. The size of the filter kernel employed can also have a significant impact on how well it performs.

On the other hand, the Adaptive Median filter is more efficient at reducing high-density noise while keeping edges and details since it adapts the filter window size based on the noise level. In conditions with significant noise, it outperforms the Median filter. However, the Adaptive Median filter can produce unevenness, and the staircase affects artifacts. The Non-Local Means filter is an advanced algorithm that uses image patches to determine how similar distinct pixels are to one another. It is better at lowering low-density noise and maintaining fine features like texture and microscopic structures than the other two filters. However, when the filter window is large, the Non-Local Means filter may introduce blurring. Also, because patch distances must be calculated, it might be computationally expensive, preventing it from being used in real-time applications.

The findings of this study might have several applications in the realm of medical imaging. The accuracy of diagnosis and treatment planning can be impacted by the quality of MRI images, which must be improved using denoising techniques. As a result, the findings of this study can aid healthcare professionals in selecting the best denoising algorithm for a particular degree of noise in MRI pictures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, for MRI pictures containing salt and pepper noise, this work examines the denoising capacities of three widely used filter algorithms: The Median filter, Adaptive Median filter, and Non-Local Means filter. Our results show that, in terms of PSNR scores, the Adaptive Median filter outperforms the other two filters—the Median filter and the Non-Local Means filter. For researchers looking to assess and contrast various denoising methods for MRI pictures, the findings of this study are indispensable.

One limitation of this study is that it only considers the typical salt and pepper noise and other types of noise may have different effects on the performance of the filters tested. Future research should examine the efficiency of these filters on various MRI picture types and assess how

well they function against other types of noise, such as Gaussian noise.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors; Raniya Ashraf, Roz Nisha, Fahad Shamim and Sarmad Shams equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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ABBREVIATIONS

PSNR	Peak Signal-To-Noise Ratio
MSE	Mean Square Error
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NLMs	Non-Local Means
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index
MR	Magnetic Resonance
SAP	Salt And Pepper Noise